

D12.4 Directions: Navigating Beyond-GDP Futures

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Disclaimer

This working paper for the project SPES has been prepared by the University of Florence as a deliverable for Work Package 12 related to Task 12.4 “Produce and disseminate a non-technical and jargon-free podcasts about the main topics addressed by SPES”. a well-designed podcast will provide the opportunity to create synergies with the ongoing public debate outside from the “academic bubble”. The specific aim of the podcast will be to present to a general audience the main issues addressed by the project and the contribution of the project in terms of achieved results.

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Introduction

In the podcast series “Directions -Navigating Beyond-GDP Futures” we explore the challenges facing our economic and social systems and dive into new perspectives that put people, the planet, and dignity back at the centre. We talk about how we conceive and measure progress, about universal social protection and human security and about why indicators and data truly matter for shaping a more sustainable future.

Our conversations are guided by the new evidence about past, present and future performances of sustainability transitions that emerged under the framework of the project SPES - Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios, funded by the Horizon Europe Programme.

The podcast series has been released at the M36, to capitalize on the work undertaken over the three-year period of the project, during which researchers worked on integrated frameworks, models, metrics and policies going beyond-GDP that support long-lasting structural change in European and Global South economies.

In each episode, Andrea Ferrannini (project manager and researcher) and Toa Giroletti (Researcher), from the University of Florence, are joined by renowned international experts that bring diverse perspectives on sustainable and inclusive well-being. Their insights help grasp what it takes to move from theory to practice, from research to action, from today’s limits to tomorrow’s possibilities.

The renowned international experts are: Kaushik Basu, Romina Boarini, Pedro Conceição, Marc Fleurbaey, Enrico Giovannini, Clara Mattei and Shahrazoub Razavi.

With our them, the interviewers unpack the limits of today’s economic model and explore concrete ideas and new directions for change. We discuss the role of policy makers, citizens, media, and institutions in shaping a fairer and more inclusive future.

Podcast episodes

How do we convince institutions to definitely go beyond-GDP?

Enrico Giovannini

In this episode, we discuss with Prof. Enrico Giovannini (full professor in Economic Statistics at the University of Rome Tor Vergata and member of the UN High-Level Expert Group on Beyond-GDP) on how to convince policymakers, national statistical institutes, citizens and media to definitely go beyond-GDP focusing their efforts on Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing.

Is reaching a consensus to go beyond-GDP possible?

Romina Boarini

In this episode, we investigate with Romina Boarini (Director of the OECD WISE Centre) how to trigger a consensus to go beyond GDP and foster Sustainable and Inclusive Wellbeing, taking into account technical, policy and public domains.

The stories behind indicators.

Pedro Conceição

In this episode, we focus on indicators. Together with Pedro Conceição (Director of the Human Development Report Office of the United Nations Development Programme), we try to go beyond the simple interpretation of indicators as numbers to discover what they actually tell us about specific situations and societies. These stories that lie beneath indicators inform on the challenges that real people face and can become a useful tool to design policies that efficiently foster Sustainable Human Development.

The urgency of fostering Sustainable Human Development.

Kaushik Basu

In this episode, we discuss with Kaushik Basu (professor in Economics at Cornell University and co-chair of the UN High-Level Expert Group on Beyond-GDP) on the urgency of fostering Sustainable Human Development across the world, based on only new theories and metrics, but mostly a renewed moral commitment by policy-makers and citizens.

Exploring the fallacy of the capitalist economic system

Clara Mattei

In this episode, together with Professor Clara Mattei (Professor of Economics at The University of Tulsa and President of FREE – Forum for Real Economic Emancipation), we unpack the limits of economic growth and the deep structural failures of our current economic system. We also explore the inputs that are needed to trigger a systemic change towards a new concept of productivity and sustainability transition.

Why is universal social protection fundamental for the future of our societies?

Shahra Razavi

In this episode, together with Shahrashoub Razavi (Director of the Social Protection Department at the International Labour Organisation), we delve deeper on the meaning of universal social protection, its role as a fundamental human right, its links to gender equality, climate action, and economic transformation, and why it is central to the future of our societies.

Tackling today's multiple crises with an integrated perspective.

Marc Fleurbaey

In this episode, we explore the complex concept of social progress with Professor Marc Fleurbaey (Paris School of Economics). We try to understand why it matters for fostering sustainability and shaping the future, and how it can help tackle today's multiple crisis, and the crucial role of measurement in understanding and driving meaningful change.

Accessibility

The podcast aims to target the general public, and in particular potential listeners with a medium to high interest in SPES related topics that may have a low level of knowledge on the same topics. The general idea was, thus, to create a new tool to transfer knowledge on the interconnections between economic growth, human flourishing, and sustainability to people outside of the academic community / decision-making processes.

The podcast is accessible on the SPES website:

<https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/directions-beyond-gdp-futures-podcast/>

The podcast has been released on the main podcasting platform:

- Spotify
<https://open.spotify.com/show/3A7NxhB9hQTyAzF7DWPdrHy>
- Apple podcast
<https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/directions-navigating-beyond-gdp-futures/id1867795204>
- Youtube Music
<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLAymy8jqy3KuUx7FH3tChg01IMATMXEV>

In order to reach as many people as possible, a communication plan to push these episodes and topics has been drafted for the two main SPES social media accounts: LinkedIn and Bluesky.

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